

The pair of scissors problem (von Harald Schröder)

The special pair of scissors problem

We view a triangle in a pair of scissors:

Now we look at the triangle more accurately:

We look for the triangle with maximum area. A is the triangle's area. The side a is known. Then we have:

$$A = \frac{c \cdot h}{2}$$

with $c = 2a \sin \beta$, $h = a \cos \beta$ and $\frac{\alpha}{2} = \beta$

h is maximum for $\beta = 0^\circ$ ($\alpha = 0^\circ$) and minimum for $\beta = 90^\circ$ ($\alpha = 180^\circ$).

Maximum area:

$$A(\beta) = a^2 \cdot \sin \beta \cdot \cos \beta$$

product rule:

$$\frac{dA(\beta)}{d\beta} = a^2 \cdot (\cos^2 \beta - \sin^2 \beta)$$

Necessary condition of local extrema:

$$\frac{dA(\beta)}{d\beta} = 0$$

Now it follows:

$$\sin^2 \beta = \cos^2 \beta \quad \Rightarrow \quad \sin \beta = \cos \beta$$

with $\tan \beta = \frac{\sin \beta}{\cos \beta}$ we obtain:

$$\tan \beta = 1 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \beta = 45^\circ \quad \alpha = 90^\circ$$

$$A_{max} = a^2 \sin 45^\circ \cos 45^\circ = \frac{a^2}{2}$$

The minimum area is in the case:

$$\alpha = \beta = 0^\circ \quad (c = 0)$$

$$\beta = 90^\circ, \alpha = 180^\circ \quad (h = 0)$$

It is $A(\beta = 0^\circ) = 0$ and $A(\beta = 90^\circ) = 0$. With $A > 0$ for $\beta \in (0^\circ, 90^\circ)$ and Rolle's theorem it follows the existence of a local maximum.

General pair of scissors problem

Now we look at a more complicated model of a pair of scissors. But this model is symplified, too.

Now the scissors have got a thickness. We introduce the following notations:

$$l = \overline{AB} \quad l_r = \overline{AC} \quad d = \overline{BD}$$

$$\alpha = \angle(A, C, E) \quad \beta = \frac{\alpha}{2}$$

$$l_r = l - \frac{d}{\tan \beta} \quad \beta \in (\beta_{min}, 90^\circ)$$

$$h = l_r \cdot \cos \beta$$

The minimum β can be determined with $l_r = 0$. It follows: $\tan \beta_{min} = \frac{d}{l}$

A is the area of the isosceles triangle (A, C, E) .

$$A = \frac{\overline{AE} \cdot h}{2} \quad \overline{AE} = l_r \cdot \sin \beta \cdot 2 \quad h = l_r \cdot \cos \beta$$

We obtain:

$$A = l_r^2 \cdot \sin \beta \cos \beta$$

$$\Rightarrow A = \left(l - \frac{d}{\tan \beta} \right)^2 \cdot \sin \beta \cos \beta$$

$$h = \left(l - \frac{d}{\tan \beta} \right) \cdot \cos \beta$$

We search the maxima $h(\beta)$ and $A(\beta)$.

The height case:

Because of $h(\beta_{min}) = h(\beta = 90^\circ) = 0$ and $h > 0$ for $\beta \in (\beta_{min}, 90^\circ)$ it follows, with Rolle's theorem, the existence of a local maximum.

We use the product rule and the reciprocal rule $\left(\frac{1}{g}\right)' = -\frac{g'}{g^2}$:

$$\frac{dh(\beta)}{d\beta} = -\sin \beta \cdot \left(l - \frac{d}{\tan \beta} \right) + \frac{d}{\cos^2 \beta \tan^2 \beta} \cdot \cos \beta$$

with $\frac{\sin \beta}{\tan \beta} = \cos \beta$:

$$= -\sin \beta \cdot l + d \cdot \cos \beta + \frac{d \cos \beta}{\sin^2 \beta}$$

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Necessary criterion of local extrema:

$$0 = \frac{dh(\beta)}{d\beta} \Rightarrow -\sin \beta \cdot \frac{l}{d} + \cos \beta + \frac{1}{\sin \beta \tan \beta} = 0$$

$$\frac{l}{d} = \frac{1}{\tan \beta} + \frac{1}{\sin^2 \beta \tan \beta}$$

$$\frac{l}{d} > 0 \quad \beta \in (0^\circ, 90^\circ)$$

We transform:

$$\frac{l}{d} \cdot \tan \beta = 1 + \frac{1}{\sin^2 \beta} \quad \sin^2 \beta = \frac{\tan^2 \beta}{1 + \tan^2 \beta}$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{l}{d} \cdot \tan \beta = 1 + \frac{1 + \tan^2 \beta}{\tan^2 \beta}$$

$$\frac{l}{d} \cdot \tan^3 \beta = \tan^2 \beta + 1 + \tan^2 \beta$$

at last:

$$\tan^3 \beta - \frac{2d}{l} \cdot \tan^2 \beta - \frac{d}{l} = 0$$

This is a polynomial of degree 3 in $\tan \beta$. This polynomial can be solved exactly. Now we will do this transformation. We introduce the substitution $\tan \beta =: x$. Then the polynomial can be written as:

$$x^3 - \frac{2d}{l} \cdot x^2 - \frac{d}{l} = 0$$

This corresponds to the normal form:

$$x^3 + rx^2 + sx + t = 0$$

We solve this equation with a method that is in Bronstein [1], chapter 2.4.2.3, p.131:

The coefficients have got the following form:

$$r = \frac{-2d}{l} \quad s = 0 \quad t = -\frac{d}{l}$$

As reduced normal form it is defined:

$$y^3 + py + q = 0$$

with

$$p = \frac{3s - r^2}{3} = -\frac{4d^2}{3l^2}$$
$$q = \frac{2r^3}{27} - \frac{rs}{3} + t = \frac{2r^3}{27} + t = -\frac{16d^3}{27l^3} - \frac{d}{l}$$

A major value is:

$$D := \left(\frac{p}{3}\right)^3 + \left(\frac{q}{2}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{-4d^2}{9l^2}\right)^3 + \left(\frac{8d^3}{27l^3} + \frac{d}{2l}\right)^2$$
$$= \frac{8}{27} \cdot \left(\frac{d}{l}\right)^4 + \frac{1}{4} \cdot \left(\frac{d}{l}\right)^2$$
$$\frac{l}{d} > 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{d}{l} > 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad D > 0$$

We obtain the following result:

There is only **one** real solution for $\frac{d}{l} > 0$. We must use **Cardan's solution of the cubic**.

Then it is valid:

$$u := \sqrt[3]{-\frac{q}{2} + \sqrt{D}}$$

Because of $D > 0$ it follows $\sqrt{D} \in \mathbb{R}, u \in \mathbb{R}$

$$v := -\frac{p}{3u} \quad p \in \mathbb{R} \quad \Rightarrow \quad v \in \mathbb{R}$$

It follows:

$y_1 = u + v \in \mathbb{R}$ is the only real solution of $y^3 + py + q = 0$.

y_2 and y_3 are complex solutions.

$$x_i = y_i - \frac{r}{3} = y_i + \frac{2d}{3l} \quad i \in 1, 2, 3$$
$$\Rightarrow \quad x_1 \in \mathbb{R} \quad \text{and} \quad x_2, x_3 \in \mathbb{C} - \mathbb{R}$$

Now we get the following result:

$$x_1 = y_1 - \frac{r}{3} = y_1 + \frac{2d}{3l}$$

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is the only one real solution of $x^3 + rx^2 + sx + t = 0$. We obtain the angles with $\tan \beta_i = x_i$ for $i \in 1, 2, 3$. β_1 is the only one real solution of the height case. β_2 and β_3 are complex because of $\tan \beta_i = x_i$ and $x_2, x_3 \in C - \mathcal{R}$.

The insertions lead to the following expression:

$$u = \sqrt[3]{\frac{8d^3}{27l^3} + \frac{d}{2l}} + \sqrt{\frac{8}{27} \cdot \left(\frac{d}{l}\right)^4 + \frac{1}{4} \cdot \left(\frac{d}{l}\right)^2}$$

$$u \geq 0$$

$$y_1 = u + v = u - \frac{p}{3u} = \frac{3u^2 - p}{3u}$$

with $p = -\frac{4d^2}{3l^2}$

$$\tan \beta_1 = x_1 = y_1 + \frac{2d}{3l} = \frac{3u^2 + \frac{4d^2}{3l^2}}{3u} + \frac{2d}{3l}$$

at last it follows:

$$\beta_1 = \arctan \left(\frac{3u^2 + \frac{4d^2}{3l^2}}{3u} + \frac{2d}{3l} \right)$$

Because of $u \geq 0$ it follows $\beta_1 \in [0^\circ, 90^\circ]$. This is the searched interval. Further it is valid that $\alpha_1 = 2 \cdot \beta_1$.

The case $\frac{d}{l} = 0$:

In this case we obtain $u = 0$ and with L'Hospital's theorem $x_1 = 0$ at last $\beta_1 = \arctan x_1 = 0$.

There is a conformity with the special pair of scissors problem. The height h is maximum at $\beta_1 = 0$. (Continuous transition from $\frac{d}{l} > 0$ to $\frac{d}{l} = 0$)

With that the formulas of u and β_1 are valid to the case $\frac{d}{l} = 0$, too.

The area case:

Now we discuss the area's formula:

$$A(\beta) = \left(l - \frac{d}{\tan \beta} \right)^2 \cdot \sin \beta \cos \beta$$

Because of $A(\beta_{min}) = A(\beta = 90^\circ) = 0$ and $A > 0$ for $\beta \in (\beta_{min}, 90^\circ)$ it follows with Rolle's theorem the existence of a local maximum.

For the calculation of the derivation we again use the product rule and the reciprocal rule $\left(\frac{1}{g}\right)' = -\frac{g'}{g^2}$.

$$\frac{d}{d\beta} \left(\left(l - \frac{d}{\tan \beta} \right)^2 \right) = 2 \cdot \left(l - \frac{d}{\tan \beta} \right) \cdot \frac{d}{\cos^2 \beta \tan^2 \beta} = 2 \cdot \left(l - \frac{d}{\tan \beta} \right) \cdot \frac{d}{\sin^2 \beta}$$

$$\frac{d}{d\beta} (\sin \beta \cos \beta) = \cos^2 \beta - \sin^2 \beta$$

Product rule:

$$\frac{dA(\beta)}{d\beta} = \frac{d}{d\beta} \left(\left(l - \frac{d}{\tan \beta} \right)^2 \right) \cdot \sin \beta \cos \beta + \left(l - \frac{d}{\tan \beta} \right)^2 \cdot \frac{d}{d\beta} (\sin \beta \cos \beta)$$

$$= 2 \cdot \left(l - \frac{d}{\tan \beta} \right) \cdot \frac{d}{\sin^2 \beta} \cdot \sin \beta \cos \beta + \left(l - \frac{d}{\tan \beta} \right)^2 \cdot (\cos^2 \beta - \sin^2 \beta)$$

These relations are valid:

$$\frac{\sin \beta}{\cos \beta} = \tan \beta \quad \cos^2 \beta = \frac{1}{1 + \tan^2 \beta} \quad \sin^2 \beta = \frac{\tan^2 \beta}{1 + \tan^2 \beta}$$

It follows:

$$\frac{dA(\beta)}{d\beta} = \frac{2d}{\tan \beta} \cdot \left(l - \frac{d}{\tan \beta} \right) + \left(l - \frac{d}{\tan \beta} \right)^2 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{1 + \tan^2 \beta} - \frac{\tan^2 \beta}{1 + \tan^2 \beta} \right)$$

Necessary criterion of local extrema:

$$\frac{dA(\beta)}{d\beta} = 0$$

Through factorization it follows:

$$l - \frac{d}{\tan \beta} = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \tan \beta = \frac{d}{l}$$

or

$$0 = \frac{2d}{\tan \beta} + \left(l - \frac{d}{\tan \beta} \right) \cdot \frac{1 - \tan^2 \beta}{1 + \tan^2 \beta}$$

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With the second equation we obtain:

$$0 = 2d \cdot (1 + \tan^2 \beta) + (l \tan \beta - d) \cdot (1 - \tan^2 \beta)$$

$$0 = 2 \cdot (1 + \tan^2 \beta) + \left(\frac{l}{d} \tan \beta - 1 \right) \cdot (1 - \tan^2 \beta)$$

$$0 = 2 + 2 \tan^2 \beta + \frac{l}{d} \cdot \tan \beta - 1 - \frac{l}{d} \cdot \tan^3 \beta + \tan^2 \beta$$

$$0 = 1 + 3 \tan^2 \beta + \frac{l}{d} \cdot \tan \beta - \frac{l}{d} \cdot \tan^3 \beta$$

It is a general polynomial of degree 3 with $\tan \beta$. The solution can be calculated exactly.

With a transformation of the polynomial we get:

$$\frac{l}{d} = \frac{1 + 3 \tan^2 \beta}{\tan \beta \cdot (\tan^2 \beta - 1)}$$

It follows:

$$\frac{l}{d} > 0 \quad \text{for} \quad \beta \in (45^\circ, 90^\circ)$$

with that for $\alpha = (90^\circ, 180^\circ)$.

Now we solve the polynomial. We put $\tan \beta =: x$. Then the polynomial becomes:

$$0 = 1 + 3x^2 + \frac{lx}{d} - \frac{lx^3}{d}$$

To normal form:

$$x^3 - \frac{3dx^2}{l} - x - \frac{d}{l} = 0$$

We again calculate the solution with Bronstein [1], chapter 2.4.2.3, p.131. The general normal form can be written as:

$$x^3 + rx^2 + sx + t = 0$$

with:

$$r = -\frac{3d}{l} \quad s = -1 \quad t = -\frac{d}{l}$$

We obtain with $y = x + \frac{r}{3}$ the reduced polynomial:

$$y^3 + py + q = 0$$

with:

$$p = \frac{3s - r^2}{3} = \frac{-3 - \frac{9d^2}{l^2}}{3} = -1 - \frac{3d^2}{l^2}$$

$$q = \frac{2r^3}{27} - \frac{rs}{3} + t = -\left(\frac{2d^3}{l^3} + \frac{2d}{l}\right)$$

$$D := \left(\frac{p}{3}\right)^3 + \left(\frac{q}{2}\right)^2 = -\left(\frac{1}{3} + \frac{d^2}{l^2}\right)^3 + \left(\frac{d^3}{l^3} + \frac{d}{l}\right)^2$$

With the cubic formula

$$(a + b)^3 = a^3 + 3a^2b + 3ab^2 + b^3$$

We obtain at last:

$$D = -\frac{1}{27} + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \left(\frac{d}{l}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{d}{l}\right)^4$$

D can be smaller, greater or equal to zero.

$D > 0 \Rightarrow$ one real solution and 2 complex solutions

$D = 0 \Rightarrow$ one real solution and a real double solution ($p \neq 0$)

$D < 0 \Rightarrow$ three real solutions

Now we have the reduced polynomial:

$$y^3 + py + q = 0$$

To the first method of solution see Bronstein [1], chapter 2.4.2.3, p.132. It is:

$$R := (\operatorname{sgn} q) \cdot \sqrt{\frac{|p|}{3}} \quad \operatorname{sgn} = \text{sign function}$$

It is $p < 0$. First we examine the case $D \leq 0$. There are three real solutions:

$$y_1 = -2R \cdot \cos \frac{\varphi}{3}$$

$$y_2 = -2R \cdot \cos \left(\frac{\varphi}{3} + \frac{2\pi}{3}\right)$$

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$$y_3 = -2R \cdot \cos\left(\frac{\varphi}{3} + \frac{4\pi}{3}\right)$$

It is:

$$\cos \varphi = \frac{q}{2R^3}$$

Now we treat the case $p < 0$ and $D > 0$. There is one real solution:

$$y_1 = -2R \cosh \frac{\varphi}{3} \quad \text{with} \quad \cosh \varphi = \frac{q}{2R^3}$$

With $x_k = y_k - \frac{r}{3}$ for $k = 1, 2, 3$ see Bronstein [1], chapter 2.4.2.3, p.131 we get the solutions of the first polynomial.

The second possibility is **Cardan's method**:

$$u := \sqrt[3]{-\frac{q}{2} + \sqrt{D}} \quad v := -\frac{p}{3u}$$

$$y_1 = u + v$$

$$y_2 = -\frac{u+v}{2} + \frac{u-v}{2} \cdot i\sqrt{3} \quad i = \sqrt{-1}$$

$$y_3 = -\frac{u+v}{2} - \frac{u-v}{2} \cdot i\sqrt{3}$$

$$x_i = y_i - \frac{r}{3} = y_i + \frac{d}{l} \quad i = 1, 2, 3$$

Now we calculate the expression of v and u :

$$v = \frac{1 + \frac{3d^2}{l^2}}{3u} = \frac{1}{u} \left(\frac{1}{3} + \frac{d^2}{l^2} \right)$$

$$u = \sqrt[3]{\frac{d^3}{l^3} + \frac{d}{l} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{d}{l}\right)^4 + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \left(\frac{d}{l}\right)^2 - \frac{1}{27}}}$$

u and v can be complex, too. ($u, v \in \mathbb{C}$)

$$\tan \beta_i = x_i \quad \beta_i = \arctan x_i \quad i = 1, 2, 3$$

To calculate the arc tangent, if x_i is complex but not real, we may need the Taylor series of arc tangent. β_i can be complex, at least one β_i must be real.

Special case $\frac{d}{7} = 0$:

It follows:

$$u = \sqrt[6]{-\frac{1}{27}} = \sqrt{-\frac{1}{3}}$$

$$v = \frac{1}{3u} = -\sqrt{-\frac{1}{3}}$$

$$x_i = y_i$$

$$x_1 = y_1 = u + v = 0$$

$$x_2 = y_2 = \frac{u-v}{2} \cdot i\sqrt{3} = -1$$

$$x_3 = y_3 = -\frac{u-v}{2} \cdot i\sqrt{3} = 1$$

$$\beta_1 = \arctan(0) = 0^\circ \quad \beta_2 = \arctan(-1) = 135^\circ \quad \beta_3 = \arctan(1) = 45^\circ$$

β_3 is corresponding to the solution of the special pair of scissors problem.

Bibliography:

- 1 I.N.Bronstein, K.A.Semendjajew, "Taschenbuch der Mathematik", Teubner Verlag, Leipzig, 22. edition 1985
- 2 Harald Schröder, "Special extreme value problems and extremum principles", Wissenschaft und Technik Verlag, Berlin, 2002